

"BEYOND PIXELS AND WORDS"

Simon DOBNIK

University of Gothenburg
Box 200, 40530 Göteborg
simon.dobnik@gu.se

ABSTRACT

Words are not used in isolation. When we communicate we relate them to our background knowledge, the intent of interaction – what is the purpose of what we want to say, who is our partner, what has been said before – our common ground, our senses and perception of the physical world and situations around us. Speech is also not the only way to convey information with: we interact in writing, symbols, with different kinds of texts, with eye-gaze, gestures and other properties of our bodies. Language models in language technology extract meaning primarily from text and sometimes a few other modalities such as images and acoustic signal. This poses two questions: (i) to what extent can these modalities be a proxy for representing semantic knowledge for different natural language processing tasks and applications; and (ii) how can we port semantic knowledge captured in these modalities to different modalities – how can we bring large language models to the real world and take them for a walk? In this talk I will describe our research towards answering these questions and outline our challenges awaiting ahead.

BIO

Simon Dobnik is a professor of computational linguistics at the Department of Philosophy, Linguistics and Theory of Science (FLoV) at University of Gothenburg, Sweden. He is a member of the Centre for Language Technology (CLT) and the Centre for Linguistic Theory and Studies in Probability (CLASP) where he leads the Cognitive systems research group. He has worked on (i) data models and machine learning of meaning representations for language, action and perception, (ii) semantic models for language, action and perception (computational semantics), (iii) representation learning in language, inference and interpretability, (iv) interpretation and generation of

spatial descriptions and reference, (v) interactive learning with small data, (vi) data bias and privacy, and (vii) multimodal dialogue, robotics and related topics.

IZVLEČEK PREDAVANJA

Besed ne uporabljamo v izolaciji. Ko govorimo, jih povezujemo s predhodnim znanjem, z namenom interakcije – s kakšnim namenom govorimo, kdo je naš sogovornik, kaj je bilo povedano prej – našim skupnim razumevanjem, s čuti in zaznavanjem fizičnega sveta in situacij okrog nas. Govor pa ni edini način, s katerim prenašamo informacije: interakcije potekajo v pisanju, simbolih, z različnimi vrstami besedil, s pogledom, gestami in drugimi lastnostmi naših teles. Jezikovni modeli v jezikovnih tehnologijah pomen primarno luščijo iz besedil, občasno pa tudi iz drugih modalnosti, kot so slike in akustični signal. To nas postavlja pred dve vprašanji: (i) v kolikšni meri te modalnosti predstavljajo in posredujejo semantično znanje za različne naloge in uporabe obdelave naravnega jezika in (ii) kako semantično znanje iz teh modalnosti prenesti v druge modalnosti – kako bi velike jezikovne modele pripeljali v resnični svet in jih peljali na sprehod? Na predavanju bom predstavil raziskave, s katerimi naslavljamo ta vprašanja, in orisal izzive, ki nas čakajo v prihodnosti.

O PREDAVATELJU

Simon Dobnik je profesor računalniškega jezikoslovja na oddelku za filozofijo, jezikoslovje in teorijo znanosti na univerzi Göteborg na Švedskem. Deluje kot član centra Centre for Language Technology (CLT) in član centra Centre for Linguistic Theory and Studies in Probability (CLASP), kjer vodi skupino za kognitivne sisteme. Njegove raziskave vključujejo: (i) podatkovne modele in strojno učenje pomenskih reprezentacij za jezik, delovanje in zaznavanje, (ii) semantične modele jezika, delovanja in zaznavanja (računalniška semantika), (iii) učenje reprezentacij v jeziku, sklepanju in razložljivosti, (iv) interpretacijo in generiranje prostorskih opisov in referenc, (v) interaktivno učenje z majhnimi količinami podatkov, (vi) pristranskost in varnost podatkov, ter (vii) multimodalni dialog, robotiko in s tem povezane teme.